

Spectrophotometric Investigation of Ti(IV) Complexes with Benzohydroxamic Acid

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The extractive spectrophotometric measurements have revealed the formation of Ti(IV) complexes with metal to ligand ratios of 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 at acidities 4N and 8N HCl respectively. A rapid method for simultaneous solvent extraction and photometric determination of microamounts of titanium is described. The stability constants, stepwise as well as overall, of 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 complexes have been evaluated by graphical extrapolation methods following Yatsimirskii's and Leden's ideas. The analytical suitability of the reagent at different acid concentrations has also been investigated.

BENZOHYDROXAMIC acid (BHA) has been utilized¹ for the gravimetric estimation of titanium. BHA has also been used for the solvent extraction and photometric estimation of many metal ions²⁻⁵. It is reported that depending on the pH, iron(III) and vanadium(V) form different complexes^{6,7}. Whether titanium also forms different complexes at varied acidities, the present investigation is undertaken taking advantage of the extractability of titanium complexes into water immiscible solvents. The present paper records simultaneous solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of microamounts of titanium with BHA. At 4N and 8N HCl medium 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 complexes are formed. This has been established by measuring absorbances of the yellow coloured solutions at 390 nm following the continuous variation^{8,9} and molar ratio¹⁰ methods. The stepwise and overall formation constants of the complexes have been evaluated by different methods¹¹⁻¹⁴ and compared. The suitability of the reagent for analytical determination of titanium in presence of diverse ions has been discussed.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions : A stock solution of titanium (2.18 mg/ml) was prepared from A. R. Potassium titanyl oxalate and was standardised¹⁵. The reagent, BHA, was prepared by the method of Blatt¹⁶. Standard reagent solutions of desired strength in A. R. isoamyl alcohol were used.

Other chemicals and solvents used in all spectrophotometric measurements were of A. R. or spectrograde quality.

Apparatus : Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm. glass cells.

Extraction Procedure : For the sake of recording absorption spectra and the effect of acid and

reagent concentration, an aliquot of titanium solution ($8.352 \times 10^{-5} M$) was taken into a 100 ml separatory funnel and adjusted to desired acidity. To 15 ml of the aqueous phase was added a desired amount of reagent solution (0.15 M) in isoamyl alcohol, the volume of the nonaqueous phase always being maintained equal to that of the aqueous phase. After shaking thoroughly the aqueous and nonaqueous phase for 5 minutes to reach equilibrium, the yellow coloured nonaqueous layer was drained out in a 50 ml beaker and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phase was subjected to extraction with a further 5 ml of isoamyl alcohol. The combined extract after drying over sodium sulphate was diluted to 25 ml with isoamyl alcohol. Equimolar solutions of titanium and the reagent ($1.823 \times 10^{-2} M$) were utilised, by incorporating two sets of complementary solutions, the volume being 6 ml and 3 ml respectively, to find the metal to ligand ratios by the methods⁸⁻¹⁰ mentioned. The absorbances of the yellow coloured complexes were measured at 390 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum : The absorbance spectra of the complex solutions, measured in the wavelength region 350-450 nm shows gradual decrease in value. As the absorbance value of the reagent solution was found appreciably low around 390 nm, all absorbance measurements were done at 390 nm against the reagent blank. Fig. 1 represents the spectral curves of Ti-BHA complexes at 4N and 8N HCl against reagent blank and of BHA against solvent blank. BHA has same absorption at 4N and 8N HCl.

Effect of reagent concentration : The metal was extracted at 4N and 8N HCl respectively with varying concentrations of the reagent. The results indicate that a single extraction with 8 ml of 0.15M

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Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of Ti-BHA Complexes.

1. ● $[R]=0.15M$, Acidity= $4N$ and $8N$ HCl.
2. ⊕ $[M]=1.67 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[R]=0.15M$, Acidity= $4N$ HCl.
3. ○ $[M]=8.3502 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[R]=0.15M$, Acidity= $8N$ HCl.

BHA was quite adequate for quantitative extraction. The colour of the complexes was found to be stable for about $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours.

Effect of acid on composition of the complexes : Titanium complexes of BHA are extractable into isoamyl alcohol from $2N$ to $9N$ HCl. The colour of the complex solution is yellow. Absorbances of different sets of complementary solutions (both Job's^{8,9} and molar ratio¹⁰ method), measured at 390 nm revealed that the complexes are predominantly $1:2$ in the acidity range $2-4N$ and $1:1$ in $7.5-9N$ HCl. For other measurements, $4N$ and $8N$ acids were used for $1:2$ and $1:1$ metal-ligand systems. The results are depicted in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error : The calibration curve for the complex systems were constructed by measuring the absorbances of different amounts of titanium, extracted according to given procedure, at 390 nm against the reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration ranges $(1-14)$ ppm and $(1-11)$ ppm at acidity $4N$ and $8N$ HCl respectively.

The optimum concentration with the highest accuracy, evaluated from Ringbom's¹⁷ curves were $(5-13)$ ppm and $(3-10)$ ppm at respective acidities.

The relative analysis error per one percent absolute photometric error, calculated according to Ayre's equation¹⁸ was 2.8 and 2.72 at the respective acidities.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity : The molar absorptivity of the complexes at acidity $4N$ and $8N$ HCl, calculated from Beer's law data are $(1.48 \pm 0.08) \times 10^3$ and $(2.32 \pm 0.02) \times 10^3$ respectively. The sensitivity, according to Sandell¹⁹ at the respective acidities are 0.031 and 0.021 μg per cm^2 .

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of diverse ions on the absorbance of Ti(IV)-BHA complexes at $4N$ and $8N$ HCl were investigated at 390 nm. Moderate amounts of ions, commonly associated with titanium were found to be tolerable. The ions having strong interference include Fe(III), Ce(IV), V(V), Mo(VI) and W(VI).

Formation constants of the complexes : Stepwise formation constants for $1:2$ system was calculated following Yatsimirskii's¹¹ and Leden's¹² method. The equilibrium ligand concentrations and the degree of complex formation were calculated from Beer's law. The construction of suitable functions and their evaluation was made in the manner stated earlier¹⁴ from data in Tables 1 and 2. The values for overall stability constants were also obtained by

Fig. 2. Job's plot.
 1. ● Ti-BHA Complex at 4N HCl
 2. ○ Ti-BHA Complex at 8N HCl
 $[M]=[R]=1.823 \times 10^{-2} M$ in each case.

Fig. 3. Molar ratio method.
 1. ○ Ti-BHA Complex at 4N HCl. Metal taken = 2ml
 2. ● Ti-BHA Complex at 8N HCl. Metal taken = 1.5 ml.
 $[M]=[R]=1.823 \times 10^{-2} M$

BAG & KHASTAGIR : SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC INVESTIGATION OF TI(IV) ETC.

TABLE 1—YATSIMIRSKII'S METHOD

Ti-benzohydroxamic acid complex

$[\text{Metal}] = [\text{Reagent}] = 1.823 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[\text{Metal}] : [\text{Reagent}] = 1 : 2$, Solvent = Isoamyl alcohol
 Metal taken = 2 ml of $1.823 \times 10^{-2} M$; Final volume = 25 ml; Time of Extraction = 5 mins.
 Absorbance for metal conc. $2.087 \times 10^{-4} M = 0.305$
 Wavelength for measurement = 390 nm.

Solution	Total ligand conc. M/lit. ($C_L \times 10^3$)	Absorbance	Equilb. Ligand conc. M/lit. ($L \times 10^3$)	Molar Extinction co-efficient ϵ ($\times 10^{-2}$)	γ ($\times 10^{-3}$)	f_1 ($\times 10^{-5}$)	f_2 ($\times 10^{-7}$)	g
1	1.8230	0.125	1.6518	0.8574	0.6053	—	—	-0.8908
2	2.5528	0.250	2.2106	1.7150	0.4523	—	—	-1.0020
3	2.9168	0.325	2.4718	2.2290	0.4044	0.9018	0.5129	-0.9940
4	3.2814	0.380	2.7612	2.607	0.3621	0.9441	0.6125	-1.007
5	3.6460	0.420	3.0710	2.880	0.3257	0.9383	0.5319	-1.0350
6	4.0106	0.480	3.3534	3.293	0.2983	0.9819	0.6170	-0.9913
7	4.3752	0.520	3.6634	3.368	0.2730	0.9736	0.5421	-1.055

TABLE 2—LEDEN'S METHOD

Solution	Total ligand conc. M/lit. ($C_L \times 10^3$)	Absorbance	Equilb. Ligand conc. M/lit. ($L \times 10^3$)	Equilb. Metal conc. M/lit. ($M \times 10^3$)	Conc. of Metal complexed M/lit. ($\times 10^3$)	Degree of complex formation $\phi = \frac{CM}{M}$	ψ_1 ($\times 10^{-1}$)	ψ_2 ($\times 10^{-4}$)
1	2.9168	0.325	2.4718	1.2355	0.2225	1.180	7.281	1.368
2	3.2814	0.380	2.7612	1.1979	0.2601	1.217	7.859	1.434
3	3.6460	0.420	3.0710	1.1705	0.2875	1.245	7.980	1.329
4	4.0106	0.480	3.3534	1.1294	0.3286	1.291	8.680	1.426
5	4.3752	0.520	3.6634	1.1021	0.3559	1.323	8.816	1.341

Harvey and Manning's method^{1,3}, using excess metal for $\log K_1$ and excess reagent for $\log K_2$. The results are given in Table 3.

 TABLE 3—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR TITANIUM COMPLEXES AT $27 \pm 2^\circ$

Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Yatsimirskii's	2.23	2.20	4.43
Leden's	1.59	2.54	4.13
Harvey and Manning's	2.25	2.25	4.50

In the normality range of acidity, titanium exists in the form of TiO^{2+} as evidenced from the formula of the isolated complexes²⁰⁻²². Therefore the 1:2 complex may be represented by the formula $[TiOR_2]$ where HR stands for BHA. It can also be concluded from the stability data in Table 3 (Yatsimirskii & Harvey-Manning's method) that the ligands acting as bidentate, attack titanium simultaneously and not in a stepwise manner. It may be noted that in a complex with high dissociating tendency, Leden's method is slightly inaccurate, as $[M]$ data are calculated, assuming Beer's Law is obeyed, but in a region where excess ligand is not present. Hence the values for $[M]$ were not exactly correct. Hence, there is discrepancy in the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in Leden's method. The structure of 1:2 complex may be depicted as

The 1:1 complex, in all probability is $[TiORCl]$

Microamounts of titanium can be determined at both 4N and 8N HCl. However, interference from V(V) is more at 8N than at 4N whereas the reverse is the situation from Mo(VI) and W(VI). Sensitivity and optimum range favour the study at 8N.

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